

#17

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

GUIDE TO THE LEADING/BLEEDING EDGE: INNOVATION CASE TRANSFER

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>INTERROGATING CREATING APPLYING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Project proposal stages; at stages when actors are interrogating/internalising new forms of knowledge and while they are co-creating/co-adapting this knowledge for application. The tool should also be used by the facilitator to evaluate their own performance at the end of the process.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Small to large multi-actor group.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical skills required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>6-8 hrs mins (depending on group size & extent of discussion).</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Requires basic materials such as sticky notes, flipchart paper and markers. Requires organisation of a physical trip to the leading edge.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tool #11, 17, 19.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: foodtank.com

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- The bleeding/leading edge tool offers participants opportunities to be introduced to innovative possibilities, emergent trends, creative approaches, and new knowledge.
- It can contribute useful knowledge and inject innovative possibilities that solve problems and inform choices on issues, challenge a group while inspiring values by enlarging visions and enhancing impact through creative new possibilities.
- It allows the facilitator to self-reflect on their injection of leading/bleeding edge principles to the process. It challenges facilitators to create a rigorous approach to visiting each case at the bleeding/leading edge.

Background and Logic

Developed by Michael Quinn-Patton, the leading/bleeding edge is a principle that connects participants to state-of-the-art.

'Leading edge refers to people or things who are the foremost or the best in technology, science, art, skill, etc. Bleeding edge technology refers to technology that is so new that it could have a high risk of being unreliable and may incur greater expense in order to use it.'

([Dictionary Reference](#)).

The leading/bleeding edge tool can be introduced to participants by the facilitator when they feel the timing is right. The tool requires the facilitator to not only be active in supporting the tool in the group, but also acting reflexively themselves in identifying new developments in evaluation, watching for emergent concepts and knowledge from research and paying attention to trends in society that are related to issues being addressed by participants.

A GUIDE criteria was developed by Michael Quinn-Patton for the identification of high-quality leading/bleeding edge cases. A high-quality case should be guiding, useful, inspiring, developmental and evaluable.

Materials

- Suitable leading/bleeding edge case
- Flipchart paper
- Sticky notes
- Thick dark markers
- Sellotape
- Pre-printed headings

Figure 1: A GUIDE for identification of high-quality leading/bleeding edge cases [Quinn-Patton \(2018\)](#).

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

Identify a suitable example which represents the GUIDE to the leading/bleeding edge.

Step 2: Introduction of the Leading-Edge Principles

- Firstly, present the principles of the leading/bleeding edge example to participants, allowing them to examine this existing knowledge and to give them insights and knowledge about the leading/bleeding edge case.
- While sitting in groups of approximately 3-8 people per group, facilitate participants to brainstorm ideas that represent their own project/initiative while also taking into mind characteristics of the leading/bleeding edge case. Write down these ideas on sticky notes and place them on sheets of flipchart paper. The facilitator should allow for around 40 minutes to complete this exercise and should walk around the room engaging with each of the groups.
- Ask each individual group to present their brainstorming ideas to the rest of the room and ask for feedback from other groups.
- Gather each group's flipchart sheets which will be used again in the future.

Step 3: Preparation for a Trip to the Leading-edge

- Identify an appropriate leading edge case to visit, engaging and communicating with the multi-actor group in selecting an appropriate case to visit.
- Facilitate participants to create group plans (following Tool #11).
- Work one-on-one with each individual group of participants to prepare group presentations for delivering as part of the visit to the leading/bleeding edge case. This offers participants an opportunity to connect their work to the latest knowledge breakthroughs and trends. It can help to expand horizons by placing each group's work in a broader societal context, even at an early stage but they are beginning to make specific decisions.

Step 4: Trip to the Leading Edge

- The trip to the leading/bleeding edge typically involves a site visit where participants can explore the case and ask questions.
- During the trip to the leading-edge, the facilitator encourages participants to ask questions throughout the day so that they can further examine the GUIDE principles of the leading/bleeding edge while also gaining knowledge.
- Facilitate participants to present their work while visiting the leading/bleeding edge and look for advice and feedback from those who have developed the leading/bleeding edge case. Feedback will encourage participants to think reflexively and may inspire them to innovatively alter their plans.

Figure 2: Participants visiting the leading edge

Figure 3: Characteristics & key principles of a 'leading edge' case visited by a multi-actor group.

Step 5: Evaluation of the Injection of Leading-Edge inputs into a Facilitation Process

Following on from the trip to the leading/bleeding edge, the facilitator completes a self assessment template which evaluates the injection of the leading-edge inputs into a facilitation process, which follows the logic of the GUIDE principles (Figure 1). The template can be found in Michael Quinn-Patton's book called [Facilitating Evaluation](#). Each question should be answered honestly by the facilitator and their reflections/considerations/ observations should be included.

Evaluation Criteria	Reflections/Observations/Considerations
1. How relevant is the input to the group's process and progress?	The trip was extremely relevant as the participants had expressed a direct interest in learning from the model. The trip helped the groups to refocus their goals and gave them encouragement and belief to continue to make progress. The trip was a turning point and without it, I think the groups would not have progressed and achieved what they did.
2. How knowledgeable am I about the input?	I was very familiar with [leading edge] having travelled there a year previously to meet the family and to discuss my project with them. I knew exactly what to expect on the day.
3. How good is the timing for the input?	The timing was excellent. Before the trip the groups had come to somewhat of a standstill and I felt that some participants were beginning to lose interest in the project. The trip injected new life and energy back into the groups and helped them to drive on.
4. How likely is this input to be well-received by the group?	The trip was well received. A number of the group participants expressed their sheer delight at the trip while others spoke less positively about it.
5. To what extent will this input help the group make progress towards its desired outcomes?	The trip allowed the four working groups to refocus and to take on board the information they learned. It also allowed them to examine first hand a 'good practice' and to interrogate that practice and rethink and refocus their goals.
6. How direct is the connection between the input and the groups issues?	Both the [leading edge] model and the project are focused on shortening food chains, reflecting culture, heritage and tradition through products and using the land and other resources to create viable enterprise opportunities. Ballymaloe represents a vision and a goal similar to that of the people of [project] so therefore there was much to be learned from [leading edge].
7. Could the input be perceived as culturally inappropriate?	No - both the model and the project are based on the use of natural resources and developing and fostering opportunities from them to create viable enterprise opportunities.
8. Any racist, sexist, homophobic, ageist, religious, political, or other innuendos that might be offensive?	No.
9. Have you used it before with success or know other who have?	No I had never before introduced a group to the leading edge. However, I was encouraged to do so by my supervisor.
10. Honestly, what are my motivations for introducing this input?	The motivations to bring the project participants to the leading-edge were to allow them to examine and question at first hand a model which they had expressed interest in learning from. The group at this time was in need of renewed focus and inspiration and the trip to [leading edge] was the obvious and appropriate step.

Figure 4: A template completed by a facilitator reflecting on their use of the leading/bleeding edge principle.

